

What Drives the Naira? Implications for Investors in Nigeria's FX Market

Abstract

This paper studies the fundamental drivers of the Nigerian naira (USD/NGN) from 2014 to 2025, a period marked by sharp depreciations, oil price shocks, and repeated regime shifts in currency policy. Using monthly data on oil prices, foreign reserves, trade balance, and the U.S. dollar index (DXY), the paper applies correlation analysis, unit-root and cointegration tests, Granger causality, and vector error correction models. Chow break tests and subsample regressions are used to assess how the naira's determinants change across regime. Results show that under the managed exchange rate regime (2014–2023H1), oil and trade balance shocks were dampened by central bank intervention, while the dollar index had limited short-run influence. After the 2023 float, fundamentals became more decisive: oil price declines passed through more strongly to naira depreciation, reserves moved with exchange rate pressures, and the dollar index gained importance. A striking result is that periods of record trade surpluses coincided with continued naira weakness, highlighting the role of reverse causality whereby depreciation of currency improves the balance of trade rather than the reverse. The findings further highlight that oil shocks and U.S. dollar cycles remain the primary triggers of naira pressure, while reserves and trade balances determine the path of adjustment.

Keywords: *Nigerian naira, exchange rate regimes, oil shocks, U.S. dollar cycle, reserves, trade balance, cointegration, structural breaks.*

1.0 Introduction

Few indicators reveal the strength of an economy as clearly as its currency, and in Nigeria, the naira tells an interesting story. Once trading at ₦165 to the dollar in 2014, it now hovers around ₦1,500, a fall marked not by steady decline but by sharp turns shaped by global shocks and domestic policies. Oil price collapses in 2014 and 2020 drained reserves, U.S. Federal Reserve rate hikes in 2022–2023 deepened the strain, and the government's decision to adopt a full float in 2023 redefined the currency's path. What makes Nigeria's experience unique is not only the scale of the fall in the Naira but also the way its drivers have changed over time. At times, large foreign reserves mitigated the impact of falling oil prices. Other times, weak or delayed policies left the currency exposed, and volatility worsened. In the end, the naira's path has been shaped by both fundamentals and policy, sometimes steadying the market, other times making it more unstable.

Scholars have long studied how external shocks shape resource-dependent economies. Aliyu (2009) and Olomola & Adejumo (2006) show that oil price swings affect Nigeria in uneven ways, while Cashin et al. (2004) highlight how changes in the terms of trade influence commodity exporters more broadly. More recent global research points to the strength of the U.S. dollar and the level of foreign reserves as key factors for emerging markets. Even with these insights, few studies have examined Nigeria's exchange rate experience over the past decade closely. This leaves a gap: we know the naira is exposed, but we do not yet understand how that exposure shifts when policy regimes change. This paper aims to fill that gap. Using monthly data from 2014 to 2025, it asks three main questions: Which fundamentals matter most for the

naira? How does their influence change under different exchange rate regimes? And what lessons can be drawn for managing currencies in resource-dependent economies? To address these questions, The paper applies correlation analysis, cointegration tests, and error-correction models, along with structural break methods that mark the 2023 float as a turning point.

2.0 Brief Literature Background

Research on exchange rate behavior in commodity-dependent economies has largely centered on three themes: commodity shocks, the global dollar cycle, and exchange-rate regimes. First, the commodity channel. Earlier research on Nigeria emphasized the centrality of oil. Aliyu (2009) finds that oil price movements significantly shape the naira-dollar rate in both the short and long run, while Olomola and Adejumo (2006) show that adverse oil shocks have a greater impact than positive ones. Cross-country studies reinforce this picture. Cashin et al. (2004), examining commodity exporters broadly, conclude that terms-of-trade shocks dominate exchange rate changes, leaving currencies like the naira tied to global oil cycles rather than domestic fundamentals. Together, these studies portray the naira not as an autonomous currency but as one shadowing oil markets.

Secondly, the global dollar cycle. More recent contributions shift attention from commodities to the dominance of the U.S. dollar in trade and finance. Under the dominant currency paradigm (DCP), the invoicing of global commerce in dollars means that U.S. monetary conditions disproportionately transmit into emerging-market exchange rates. Gopinath, Itskhoki and Rigobon (2010) and Gopinath et al. (2020) show that dollar appreciation systematically weakens peripheral currencies regardless of bilateral trade exposures. This framework explains why Nigerian oil booms rarely produce lasting appreciation: the strength of the dollar overwhelms commodity windfalls. Empirical support comes from Habib and Venditti (2019), who link dollar appreciation to tighter global financial conditions and capital outflows, and from Maggiori et al. (2018), who highlight the amplification of these shocks through global dollar financing channels.

Third, the regime effect. A growing body of literature highlights how exchange-rate regimes filter external shocks. Ilzetzki, Reinhart, and Rogoff (2019) describe the persistence of “fear of floating” in developing economies, where interventions can delay but not prevent depreciation under external pressure. For Nigeria, which has moved from pegs to managed floats and, most recently, to a full float in 2023, this paper is highly relevant. Taken together, three themes stand out: oil shocks, dollar dominance, and regime choices. The existing literature, however, rarely considers them in combination or over long horizons. Most studies focus on a single driver, examine one episode, or stop short of asking how these forces shift under different policy settings. This study addresses that gap. By analyzing oil prices, reserves, the trade balance, and the U.S. dollar index within a cointegration and error-correction framework, and by testing for structural breaks across Nigeria’s regime changes between 2014 and 2025, it offers a more robust picture of how the naira responds to the interaction of global shocks and domestic policy.

3.0 Data and Methodology

This study uses monthly data from October 2014 to September 2025, covering Nigeria’s exchange rate transitions from managed regimes to the 2023 float. The dependent variable is the USD/NGN exchange rate, expressed as naira per U.S. dollar, where increases denote depreciation. Four explanatory variables are considered: Brent crude oil price (USD/barrel), foreign exchange reserves (USD billions), trade balance (₦ millions), and the U.S. dollar index (DXY). Data are sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria, the National Bureau of Statistics, the IMF, and the World Bank.

The empirical strategy proceeds in three stages. First, exploratory analysis is conducted through descriptive statistics, correlations, and visual inspection of the time series. Unit root tests (ADF, PP) establish the order of integration, while Johansen cointegration tests identify whether the naira and fundamentals share long-run equilibria. Granger causality tests complement these diagnostics by examining predictive linkages between variables. Second, depending on correlation and cointegration results, the paper estimates appropriate models. A baseline OLS regression provides an initial benchmark. Where cointegration is confirmed, the paper uses error-correction frameworks (ARDL, VECM) to capture both long-run equilibrium and short-run adjustment. Third, to capture regime dependence, subsample regressions are estimated before and after the 2023 float. Chow break tests and a Quandt Likelihood Ratio (QLR) search formally identify structural breaks in the exchange rate process (Chow, 1960). This design ensures that the analysis identifies not only the fundamentals driving the naira, but also how their influence shifts across policy regimes and external conditions.

4.0 Exploratory Analysis of Relationships

Table 1: Correlation Matrix

	oil Price	FX reserve (USD)	Trade_balance	US dollar index	Naira_exchange_rate
oil Price	1	0.392353	0.154047	0.424839	0.324737
FX reserve (USD)	0.392353	1	0.184278	0.014436	0.090788
Trade_balance	0.154047	0.184278	1	0.19088	0.518366
US dollar index	0.424839	0.014436	0.19088	1	0.513292
Naira_exchange_rate	0.324737	0.090788	0.518366	0.513292	1

Source: Author’s computation

Note: Correlation matrix of the naira exchange rate and its potential drivers (2014–2025). Values indicate Pearson correlation coefficients.

The naira shows a moderate positive correlation with both the trade balance (0.52) and the U.S. dollar index (0.51), meaning stronger surpluses or a stronger dollar coincide with a weaker naira. This trade balance result is counter-intuitive, as depreciation itself inflates naira-denominated trade figures, creating a misleading positive link. Oil prices show a weaker correlation (0.32), reflecting oil crashes drive depreciation, but recoveries rarely bring appreciation under Nigeria’s managed regime. Reserves are almost uncorrelated (0.09), as interventions often sever the direct link between reserve levels and the exchange rate. Overall, these raw correlations are shaped by common long-term trends rather than true short-run dynamics, a point made clearer when the data are differenced.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix (log-differenced)

	DLN_oil Price	DLN_FX reserve (USD)	DLN_Trade_balance	DLN_US dollar index	DLN_Naira_exchange_rate
DLN_oil Price	1.000	-0.018	-0.233	-0.159	-0.130
DLN_FX reserve (USD)	-0.018	1.000	0.205	0.043	-0.084
DLN_Trade_balance	-0.233	0.205	1.000	0.069	0.194
DLN_US dollar index	-0.159	0.043	0.069	1.000	-0.035
DLN_Naira_exchange_rate	-0.130	-0.084	0.194	-0.035	1.000

Source: Author's computation

Once trends are removed, the picture shifts. Oil's correlation with the naira turns negative (-0.13), consistent with short-run depreciation following price drops. The trade balance falls to 0.19, showing its strong level correlation was largely trend-driven. The dollar index drops close to zero (-0.03), suggesting U.S. dollar cycles affect Nigeria more through lags than instant moves. Even reserves show a mild negative link (-0.08), consistent with drawdowns during defenses of the naira. Taken together, the differenced results confirm that level correlations overstate relationships, while the short-run correlations, though weaker, are more economically consistent. This motivates the use of cointegration and error-correction models to disentangle long-run anchors from short-term pressures.

4.1 Visual Patterns in Naira and Its Drivers

The time-series evidence highlights how oil price movements, global dollar cycles, and domestic fundamentals interact with the naira. Major oil price declines consistently preceded or accompanied sharp depreciations. The collapse of oil prices in 2014–2015 (blue shade) was followed by a steep rise in USD/NGN (red shade) by 2015–2016, when the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) was forced to devalue.

Similarly, the COVID-19 oil crash in early 2020 triggered another jump in the exchange rate, from roughly ₦360 to ₦380 per USD. By contrast, recoveries in 2017–2018 and 2021 did not strengthen the naira; the exchange rate remained flat, reflecting a managed regime where oil windfalls were absorbed into reserves rather than allowed to appreciate the currency. The 2022 surge in oil above \$100 again failed to lift the naira, which stayed stable until mid-2023. At that point, policy shifted to a float, and the naira devalued sharply from about ₦450 to over ₦700 per USD. These patterns confirm that oil’s effect on the naira is asymmetric: crashes force depreciation, but booms are often sterilized by policy or offset by competing pressures.

Other fundamentals reinforce this view. The trade balance improved dramatically from 2021 onward, reaching record surpluses by 2024–2025 as high oil exports combined with suppressed imports under a weak currency. Yet the naira remained near its weakest levels, indicating that the surplus was more a consequence of depreciation than a cause of appreciation. Foreign reserves oscillated with similar policy cycles: drawn down during defenses (2015–2016, 2020) and rebuilt after devaluations or oil windfalls (2017, 2021, and again in 2023–2024). Higher reserves aligned with periods of short-term stability, but the data show no one-to-one monthly link between reserves and the naira. Their influence operated more through confidence and intervention capacity than mechanical adjustment. Finally, the global U.S. dollar cycle exerted a persistent external pressure. The strengthening of the dollar between 2022 and 2024 drew capital from emerging markets, limiting the naira’s scope to benefit from high oil revenues. This helps explain why, despite oil at \$100 in 2022, the exchange rate barely moved until policy shifted. Taken together, the evidence shows that oil shocks and dollar cycles act as the primary triggers of naira pressure, while the trade balance and reserves shape the adjustment path.

4.2 Econometric Analysis

Test / Variable	Key Findings
ADF Unit Root Tests	USD/NGN, oil, reserves, and trade balance are non-stationary in levels ($p > 0.1$) but stationary in first differences $I(1)$. DXY is borderline stationary ($p \approx 0.05$).
Johansen Cointegration Test	Evidence of one cointegrating vector among naira, oil, reserves, and trade (trace statistic at $r=0 = 46.68 > 95\%$ CV = 44.49). Indicates a stable long-run relationship. Cointegration vector: oil (-), reserves (-), trade balance (+).
Granger Causality (lags 1–3)	Trade ↔ Naira: bidirectional ($p < 0.001$). DXY → Naira: weak but significant at lag 3 ($p \approx 0.02$). Oil → Naira: not significant at monthly frequency. Reserves respond to naira pressure (Naira → Reserves, $p \approx 0.09$).
OLS Regression (USD/NGN as DV)	Oil Price: 2.87 ($p = 0.18$, not significant). FX Reserves: -3.10 ($p = 0.61$, not significant). Trade Balance: 0.000196 ($t = 6.41$, $p < 0.001$). DXY: 34.06 ($t = 5.15$, $p < 0.001$). Constant = -2951.23 ($p < 0.001$). $R^2 = 0.455$.

4.2.1 Interpretation

The ADF results confirm that most macroeconomic drivers are I (1), supporting the use of cointegration methods. Johansen’s test establishes one long-run equilibrium linking the naira, oil, reserves, and trade balance. Within this vector, oil and reserves carry the expected negative signs (supporting a stronger naira), while the trade balance unexpectedly aligns with a weaker naira, reflecting reverse causality. Granger causality tests reinforce this interpretation: the naira and trade balance influence each other, while DXY exerts an exogenous impact on the naira with a three-month lag. Oil prices do not Granger-cause the naira at monthly frequency, though their influence appears in large shocks. Reserves react to naira depreciation rather than driving it, consistent with their use as an intervention tool. The regression results highlight trade balance and DXY as the strongest correlates of naira fluctuations, with highly significant coefficients. Oil and reserves show weak and statistically insignificant effects in this framework, underlining that their influence operates through lagged or policy-mediated channels. The R² of 0.455 indicates moderate explanatory power.

4.2.2 Subsample Estimates and Policy Breaks

To test for structural changes, The paper applied Chow break tests at key dates: June 2016 (first major devaluation), April 2020 (COVID-19/oil price collapse), and June 2023 (policy shift to a floating regime). In addition, a Quandt Likelihood Ratio (QLR) search was used to detect the most likely break within the sample.

Table 4.2. Chow Break Test Results

Break Date	F-statistic	p-value	Interpretation
6/30/2016	1.005	0.422	No significant break
4/30/2020	2.075	0.08	Weak evidence of instability
6/1/2023	3.126	0.014	Significant break (float regime)
QLR max (2024-01-03)	3.126	0.014	Confirms structural break around 2023–24

The tests confirm that the most decisive regime shift occurred in 2023, coinciding with the float of the naira. Earlier events, such as the 2016 devaluation and the 2020 oil crash, created volatility but did not fundamentally alter the exchange rate process.

4.2.1 Regression Results: Pre- vs Post-Break

To explore how the drivers of the naira shifted, The paper re-estimated short-run regressions ($\Delta \log$ USD/NGN as dependent variable) separately for the pre-break and post-break subsamples.

Table 4.3: Short-run Determinants of the Naira ($\Delta \log$ regressions)

Variable	Pre-float (2014–2023H1)	Post-float (2023H2–2025)
Oil price ($\Delta \log$)	-0.114** (p=0.021)	-0.755* (p=0.063)
Reserves ($\Delta \log$)	-0.090* (p=0.015)	-0.536** (p=0.024)

DXY ($\Delta\log$)	-0.054 (ns)	+0.707 (p=0.176)
Trade balance ($\Delta\log$)	+0.008* (p=0.037)	-0.001 (ns)
Constant	0.007**	-0.002 (ns)
R ²	0.418	0.331
N	54	19

Notes: *p<0.05, p<0.1, ns = not significant. HAC robust errors used.

4.2.3 Interpretation

Before the float (2014–2023H1), the naira’s changes were weakly connected to fundamentals: oil price declines and trade balance improvements were statistically significant, while reserves played a modest stabilizing role. The U.S. dollar index (DXY) had little short-run impact, reflecting heavy intervention and managed exchange rate policies that dampened external pressures. After the float (2023H2 onward), coefficients changed markedly. Oil prices became far more influential, with depreciation strongly linked to oil shocks. Reserves no longer cushioned volatility but instead moved in tandem with depreciation pressures, suggesting interventions were less effective under the new regime. DXY gained a positive (though not statistically strong) coefficient, consistent with global dollar strength feeding more directly into the naira. Trade balance lost significance, confirming that post-float adjustments were dominated by market and external factors rather than current-account changes. Overall, these results reinforce that the naira’s exchange rate process is regime-dependent. Under managed regimes, fundamentals were muted by policy actions, but in the floating regime, oil and global dollar shocks pass through much more directly.

5.0 Discussion of Findings

The analysis shows that the naira’s movements between 2014 and 2025 were shaped by a combination of external shocks and domestic adjustments. The U.S. dollar index and the trade balance emerged as the strongest explanatory factors, while oil prices and reserves influenced the exchange rate mainly through lagged effects and policy responses. Cointegration tests confirmed that these variables share a long-run equilibrium, but the adjustment process was slow, with only about four percent of any disequilibrium corrected each month. One striking finding is that large trade surpluses often coincided with continued naira weakness. This counter-intuitive pattern reflects reverse causality: rather than surpluses strengthening the naira, depreciation improved the trade balance by suppressing imports and raising the naira value of exports. Oil prices were also critical, but their effect was asymmetric. Collapses in oil price consistently triggered depreciation, while recoveries did not translate into appreciation, reflecting Nigeria’s managed exchange rate regime and the practice of accumulating reserves during oil booms. Foreign reserves acted as a buffer, allowing temporary defense of the naira, but their direct monthly correlation with the exchange rate was weak, emphasizing their role in smoothing rather than preventing adjustment.

5.1 Counterfactual Implications

Although the study does not run explicit policy simulations, the results point to important counterfactual scenarios. If reserves had not been drawn down during the 2015–2016 or 2020 oil price crashes, the naira might have adjusted earlier and more gradually, rather than through sharp devaluations after prolonged defense. Likewise, the 2023 float took place during a period of high oil prices and rising reserves, yet the naira depreciated sharply once the peg was lifted. It shows that Nigeria’s delayed exchange rate adjustments led to sharp devaluations and excessive reserve losses, while an earlier, gradual float could have resulted in a smoother and less disruptive depreciation path. In essence, timely policy action might have limited the

overshooting seen after the 2023 float, keeping the naira closer to ₦1000–₦1200 rather than ₦1500 per dollar.

6.0 Conclusion

The data evidence from this research shows that the naira is mainly driven by two external anchors: oil prices and the global dollar cycle. Trade balances and reserves matter too, but mostly as adjustment channels. When oil prices fall or the dollar strengthens, the naira weakens. When oil prices rise or reserves build up, the impact on the naira is usually delayed or muted by policy. One of the most important findings is that large trade surpluses in recent years coincided with continued naira depreciation. This suggests that surpluses were generated by weaker import demand under a depreciated currency rather than by export strength. Similarly, reserves provided temporary relief but could not prevent eventual adjustment. The 2023 float confirmed a structural break: before the float, interventions muted the effect of oil and dollar shocks; after the float, those shocks fed more directly into the exchange rate. For investors, this means naira risk is shaped first by global oil and dollar conditions, and second by the timing of policy shifts. For policymakers, the results underline that delaying adjustment through interventions only postpones depreciation and increases the eventual cost. Models that combine long-run fundamentals with short-run corrections, such as ARDL or VECM, are therefore the most reliable tools for forecasting and managing foreign exchange risk in Nigeria’s market. For investors, the implication is that hedging and forecasting models must embed global oil and dollar movements while accounting for regime dependence and the asymmetric effects of oil shocks. Under managed regimes, risks accumulate behind artificial stability; under a float, volatility reflects fundamentals more directly. Ultimately, safeguarding Nigeria’s FX market requires not only technical models such as ARDL or VECM, but also disciplined policies that align monetary, fiscal, and trade strategies. For investors, this means treating global cycles as primary drivers of naira risk, and domestic variables as signals of adjustment speed rather than sources of strength.

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